

CONSTITUTION —IS THE GUARANTEE OF A PROSPEROUS MARRIAGE AND A PROSPEROUS LIFE

Sarvar Saidov Faxriddin o'gli

3-year student of the Faculty of Jurisprudence of Karakalpak State University named after Berdak

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7869568>

Abstract. *At the same time, this article is about the assumptions about the Referendum 2023, which is expected to be held in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and its prospects, and it talks about the great importance of the Constitution for the prosperity and well-being of the people.*

Keywords: *Republic of Uzbekistan, constitution, prosperous life, prosperous life, people, Uzbek people, freedom of citizens.*

INTRODUCTION.

Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan is taking bold steps on the path of new development and success. The reforms implemented in all areas are primarily aimed at ensuring the well-being of the people and decent lifestyle and conditions of citizens.

The Basic Law of the country stipulates that a person's life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights are the highest value. People have faith in justice and the rule of law. The main thing is that the desire of citizens of the country to participate in solving problems in life and social processes is growing day by day.

At the same time, in order for the current laws to function fully, to serve the full implementation of the relations between the individual, society and the state, in a word, to implement the reforms in practice, citizens must have legal consciousness and legal culture. is necessary. Community life and lifestyle will change only when all citizens develop a sense of respect for the Constitution and laws and the need to comply with them.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY.

For this reason, it is necessary to organize events that inform citizens about the place and role of the Constitution in the national legal system. In addition, it is very important to expand students' knowledge about the main law - the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and to increase students' legal literacy. The organization of spiritual and educational hours in neighborhoods, the introduction of lectures on the Constitution of Uzbekistan, its origin, main tasks and state symbols - the national anthem, national flag and coat of arms of Uzbekistan are also part of the awareness of citizens. Rida not only expands his knowledge, but also serves in the formation of respect and attention to the General Dictionary, the qualities of not paying attention to the processes related to it in society.

If it is permissible by experts in the relevant field, it should be emphasized that the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a strong support and legal guarantee of the development of society, a bright symbol of the independence of the Motherland, using mass media. Also, videos and short films should be presented to the Uzbek people proving that its adoption has become one of the most important stages of the country's sovereignty.

The Basic Law laid the foundation for the implementation of large-scale reforms in the political, economic and social spheres, ensuring human rights and freedoms, peace and harmony in society. It serves as a solid legal basis for the consistent development of social relations and

determines the vector of mutual relations between citizens, society and the state. The core of the constitutional right is the current Constitution itself. The place and role of the Constitution in any national legal system is considered fundamental and important. In addition, each country has its own Constitution. It should be noted that there is no single universal constitutional model for all countries and it cannot be. Each country has its own constitutional development path. In this regard, the Constitution of independent Uzbekistan is no exception.

RESULTS.

It is emphasized on a global scale that, in addition to being the main foundation for the development and progress of an independent democratic legal state, it is also a condition for this state to have the Constitution. During the years since the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its norms and rules have been consistently applied to life. Significant progress has been made in all aspects of the life of the Uzbek people, and such progress is still ongoing. Thanks to the Constitution, harmony between citizens and nationalities has been ensured in the country, the standard of living has increased year by year, and high goals have been achieved in the fields of socio-cultural development, education, science and sports.

Young people, who are the owners of the future, are getting theoretical and practical information about the history of the Constitution of Uzbekistan, the principles of the constitutional system, the symbols and principles of sovereignty and democracy expressed in the main law of the country. It is no exaggeration to say that this is also the result of the articles on the rights and obligations of a person and their implementation, enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic.

The representatives of the younger generation are learning the freedom to boldly answer any question about the Constitution with their ingenuity. They also have the right to express their views on important issues of the electoral legislation. Not only young people, but the entire Uzbek people have this right. For this reason, the participation of people's representatives in the practical processes of Referendum 2023, which is being organized in connection with the new version of the Constitution, is considered important, and all the necessary conditions are being prepared for their free voting.

DISCUSSION.

The principles and rules defined in the Constitution, long-term goals and tasks, and a well-thought-out development strategy have defined fundamental reforms in all areas. It was a reliable and decisive factor that made Uzbekistan achieve high goals. Citizens of the country can rightfully be proud of this.

The General Dictionary is also the result of reforms that meet the modern democratic requirements for the formation of a national statehood and political system to ensure the liberalization and democratization of society, the sustainable growth of the economy, the well-being of the population and the quality of life.

If we summarize the work done in the past years, today there is a good reason to say that great work has been done to renew and reform the republic and achieve macroeconomic balance. The Constitution is the legal and legislative basis for establishing an independent, sovereign democratic state, ensuring the priority of private property in the conditions of a multi-sectoral market economy and providing guarantees for its protection, as well as the formation of civil society in the country. On this basis and because of the Constitution, human interests, rights and freedoms become the highest value.

In this regard, it was allowed to make additions and amendments to some articles of the Constitution. And in connection with this, at the same time, referendum 2023, that is, a free vote on the new version of the Constitution, is being carried out in the country. In this case, the introduction of innovations based on the introduction of a completely new system free from dogmas and patterns in the field of education and training will become a real historical event of the past, which arouses great interest in the whole world. As a result of this, today a new generation that thinks independently and meets the requirements of the time will be formed, and tomorrow, a broad group of young people who are able to take responsibility for the fate of the Motherland will step onto the field.

CONCLUSION.

Practice has shown that the process of reforming and democratizing all aspects of the country's life is not a one-time thing, but a continuous process that has the ultimate goal of implementing all the principles and rules of the Constitution. This will serve to further prosperity of the country, to strengthen its freedom and independence.

The basic law clearly states that the main goal of Uzbekistan is to build not only a democratic legal state, but also a fair society. Therefore, its essence is to create decent living conditions for people, to implement the principles of social justice as the basis of all areas of national legislation. Without deviating from this, additions and amendments to the Constitution are about to be introduced today as a consistent continuation of the listed goals. All these actions are necessary for the well-being of the people, for the citizens to live in perfect conditions, in a word, to live in a prosperous lifestyle, including the expansion of the range of rights and freedoms of women, the increase of opportunities, and the prospective education of young people. serves for quick and complete implementation of measures.

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